
182. The YORP effect

IN ESSAY 181, I looked at the effect of solar radiation on the orbits of minor solar system bodies. To recap, depending on orbit, size, spin rate and composition, solar radiation can ‘push’ an object away from the Sun through radiation *pressure* or, for particles less than a few mm, act as a ‘headwind’, slowing its orbital speed, and sending it inwards (the Poynting–Robertson effect).

For a rotating body, the incident solar flux can lead to re-radiated but delayed thermal emission, sending the object outwards or inwards depending on whether its rotation is prograde or retrograde (the Yarkovsky effect). The momentum transfer is minute, but can result in significant orbit evolution over tens of millions of years.

The YORP effect (Yarkovsky–O’Keefe–Radzievskii–Paddack) is a second-order effect, influencing the spin rate and spin axis orientation of small *irregular* asteroids. Like the Yarkovsky force, its effects accumulate over long periods, resulting in some rather remarkable changes in the properties of the asteroid population.

I will describe what YORP is, expand more on its scientific importance, and what Gaia has to say about it.

THE TERM acknowledges four contributions to the understanding of how solar electromagnetic radiation, through diffuse reflection, absorption, and thermal re-emission, changes a body’s angular momentum relative to its centre of mass, and dependent on its detailed properties such as shape and albedo (Rubincam, 2000).

Specifically, the term encapsulates Yarkovsky’s realisation (1901) that the thermal radiation carries momentum as well as heat, Radzievskii’s suggestion (1954) of rotation driven by changes in albedo, Paddack’s realisation that shape was more effective in altering a body’s spin rate, and Paddack and O’Keefe’s suggestion that the various effects can lead to rotational ‘bursting’, with small asymmetric bodies eventually reduced to dust (Paddack, 1969; Paddack & Rhee, 1975).

With asteroids being irregular in shape, and having rotation periods of order days, being much shorter than their orbital periods, the YORP effect is the secular change in its rotation state after averaging the solar radiation torques over the body’s spin and orbital periods.

THE YORP effect is presumed responsible for the many asteroids with very high and very low spin. Those with diameter ≥ 125 km follow a Maxwell distribution, while 50–125 km sizes show an excess of fast rotators. The smallest, $\lesssim 50$ km, have an excess of very fast and slow rotators, becoming more pronounced with decreasing size (Rubincam, 2000; Kaasalainen et al., 2007).

Direct confirmation of the YORP effect came with optical observations of the 100-m diameter asteroid 2000 PH5, later designated (54509) YORP. Over 4 years, the 12-min rotation period showed a continuously increasing spin rate of $2.0 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-4}$ deg d⁻² which could not be explained by gravitational torques (Lowry et al., 2007; Taylor et al., 2007). A radar image and 3d model is given at [the object’s wiki page](#).

Similar results were found for the 1-km sized asteroid (1862) Apollo, where the change is clearly visible in the long-term light curve, amounting to an extra rotation in just 40 yr (Kaasalainen et al., 2007; Ďurech et al., 2024). Predictions for (25143) Itokawa were made by Vokrouhlický et al. (2004) and Scheeres et al. (2007), and duly confirmed by Kitazato et al. (2007), although sensitive to its assumed surface topography (Breiter et al., 2009; Statler, 2009; Lowry et al., 2014; Walsh, 2018).

Today, the YORP effect has been identified individually for just 12 asteroids (Ďurech et al., 2008; Ďurech et al., 2022; Ďurech et al., 2024, Table 1). Gaia DR3 has contributed no others, and DR4 is also likely to be of too short a duration for additional detections.

BUT THERE IS *indirect* evidence for its role in the orbital evolution of asteroids over long periods, most prominently in the clustering of the directions of rotation axes in asteroid families (Vokrouhlický & Čapek, 2002; Bottke et al., 2006; Vokrouhlický et al., 2006).

Extreme YORP-driven spin-up may also explain asteroid fragmentation (Paddack, 1969; Paddack & Rhee, 1975; Veras & Scheeres, 2020), including the observed breakup of asteroid P/2013 R3 (Jewitt et al., 2014).

It may also be important in the formation of binary asteroids (Walsh et al., 2008), and asteroid pairs with very similar orbits (Vokrouhlický & Nesvorný, 2008).

ALL THE WORK that I have described so far pre-dates any use of the Gaia data. I will now look at what insights Gaia is contributing in the area of the YORP effect, over and above the results on the Yarkovsky effect which I considered in essay 181. That is, I will focus on the use of Gaia photometry for studies of asteroid rotation.

In fact, the following results come mainly from a study by Āurech & Hanuř (2023) on the ‘Reconstruction of Asteroid Spin States from Gaia DR3 Photometry’.

I WILL FIRST recall the contents of Gaia DR3 most relevant for this particular study. DR3 includes accurate photometry for 154 787 solar system bodies, covering a time interval of 34 months, between July 2014–May 2017 (essay 76). With some 3 million measurements in total, the number of photometric observations per asteroid ranges from a few to several tens. And, remarkably, their spins can be determined in many cases.

To estimate the spin state and shape of each asteroid, Āurech & Hanuř (2023) computed the illumination geometry for each observation, and used light-curve inversion to find the best-fit physical model. This was parameterised by the sidereal rotation period, the spin axis direction, and a low-resolution convex shape.

To find the best-fit model, they tried tens of thousands of trial periods in the range 2–10 000 h, with tens of trial pole directions. To establish the correct rotation period, they also used a triaxial ellipsoid model as an approximation to the asteroid shape. Some examples for asteroid (43) Ariadne are shown here (from their Fig. 3).

For more than 8600 of the original 150 000 objects, they were able to determine the spin state, together with a low-resolution convex shape model. Their results are limited to objects for which they found just two solutions for the rotation poles, (λ_1, β_1) and (λ_2, β_2) in ecliptic coordinates, and for which the two differed by less than some (small) selected values of $\Delta\lambda$ and $\Delta\beta$.

Their first 10 objects are tabulated here (an extract of their Table 3). It gives the two pole solutions, the identified period, and the number of observations used in the solution. Remarkably, the uncertainty on the rotation period is on the order of the last decimal place.

They also include a column, omitted here, giving the method used for computing their periodograms: C (convex shape models), E (ellipsoidal models), and CE (where both methods gave the same period).

Asteroid	λ_1 [deg]	β_1 [deg]	λ_2 [deg]	β_2 [deg]	P [h]	N_{obs}
5 Astraea	122	37	312	40	16.8008	36
26 Proserpina	83	-46	255	-56	13.1092	58
32 Pomona	103	39	279	41	9.4475	38
33 Polyhymnia	20	-29	197	-31	18.6088	36
41 Daphne	207	-35	355	-39	5.98807	35
43 Ariadne	69	-10	252	-12	5.76182	53
44 Nysa	96	45	287	54	6.4214	25
45 Eugenia	123	-32	299	-20	5.69918	30
48 Doris	107	32	291	45	11.8900	50
50 Virginia	103	12	281	26	14.3107	31

THIS LARGE SAMPLE of new asteroid models compares very favourably with previous results based on a similar modelling approach. Such results include 18 solutions, of which 10 were new, from BlueEye600 (Āurech et al., 2018b); 173 solutions, 129 new, from Gaia DR2 (Āurech & Hanuř, 2018); 1100 solutions, 762 new, from Gaia DR2 and Lowell (Āurech et al., 2019); 900 solutions, 662 new, from Lowell and WISE (Āurech et al., 2018a); and 2750 solutions, of which there were about 1800 new, from ATLAS photometry (Asteroid Terrestrial-impact Last Alert System; Āurech et al., 2020).

Gaia DR3 has increased by more than a factor two the numbers of asteroids with known spin states and rotation poles (viz. 8600 compared with 3500 previously listed in the DAMIT data base; Āurech et al., 2010), with a significant advance in the study of their spin properties. One of their figures, included here, shows the distribution of period versus diameter for the Gaia DR3 solutions, and those from the Asteroid Lightcurve Database (LCDB, Warner et al., 2009), as of December 2021.

THE RESULTS of Āurech & Hanuř (2023) all go in the direction of confirming previous findings, but with much greater confidence. And they give a foretaste for the larger samples that will be available with Gaia DR4.

First, small asteroids have poles clustered toward the ecliptic poles, an effect attributed to, and well-explained by, the YORP-induced spin evolution. Second, asteroid migration due to the Yarkovsky effect depends on the spin orientation. Third, the sense of rotation of members of asteroid families are correlated with their semi-major axis. Thus, over the age of the family, orbits of prograde rotators have evolved, due to the Yarkovsky effect, to larger semi-major axes, while those of retrograde rotators have drifted in the opposite direction.